

Experiments and Procedure for Examination of RTM Process Parameters for Obtaining Class A Surface Finish

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SUMMARY: Resin Transfer Molding (RTM) has great potential as an efficient and economical process for fabricating large and complicated composite structural components. For high volume production such as in automotive applications, RTM is attractive because of low capital investment cost required and process versatility in component integration and assembly. One of the challenges facing the automotive field is the resulting surface finish of manufactured components. The main objective of this research is first to understand the parameters affecting the RTM process, especially those affecting the surface finish of final parts, by a strategic experimental program.

The chemical composition, manufacturing parameters (temperature, pressure) and tooling have been identified as the main parameters that affect the surface finish of the final part. Molding parameters like molding temperature, ΔT (upper and lower mold temperature), injection rate (or pressure), rate of cure and injection temperatures must also be optimized. The Taguchi Method for design of experiments (DOE) will be used to study the effect of different parameters on the surface finish aspects of finished parts.

An experimental program will be outlined consisting of several RTM injections of parts, based on the parameters defined by the Taguchi Method. A flat plate mold with dimensions 18" by 18" has been designed to produce a number of parts in order to study the effect of above-mentioned parameters on the surface finish. The results of the experiments will be a better understanding of surface finish aspects of the RTM process.

KEYWORDS: Resin transfer molding, surface finish, optimization, Taguchi method, experiments, control factors, automotive composites, molding parameters, tooling

INTRODUCTION

Resin Transfer Molding (RTM), also referred to (including its various process variants) as liquid composite molding, is increasingly being used in the aerospace and automotive industries. This family of related processes allows the molding of components with complex shapes and large surface areas. RTM is a process suited for short and medium production runs and is employed in many different applications. Some of the benefits afforded by RTM include low capital investment, tooling flexibility and the ability to mold large and complex shapes with ribs, cores and inserts. It also allows greater parts integration and a range of resin systems and fibrous reinforcements are available for RTM injection with a controllable fiber volume fraction. (see Niu (1)).

RTM PROCESS

In this process (Figure 1), a dry reinforcement material that has been cut and shaped into a preformed piece, generally called a preform, is placed in a prepared mold cavity. Once the mold has been closed and clamped shut, resin is injected into the mold cavity, where it flows through the reinforcement preform, expelling the air in the cavity and wetting out or impregnating the reinforcement. When excess resin begins to flow from the vent areas of the mold, the resin flow is stopped and the molded component begins to cure. When cure is completed, which can take from several minutes to hours, it is removed from the mold and the process can begin again to form additional parts. A detailed description of the whole procedure can be found in Ludick (2).

Fig. 1 Schematics of the Resin Transfer Molding process

SURFACE FINISH ASPECTS

In the manufacturing of polymer composites, RTM is thought to be an efficient and economical process for fabricating large and complicated structural components. However RTM has not fulfilled its potential for use in high volume applications. Surface finish of the part in these applications is the foremost concern, especially in automotive industry, which is striving to achieve *Class A surface finish*. Class A surface finish is thought to exhibit aspects of flatness, smoothness and light reflection similar to that of finished stamped steel sheeting, typically with a DORRI (Distinctness of Retro Reflective Image) value of 60-90, as measured by Mathews et al. (3) using the D-sight optical enhancement technique.

Class A finish is a perfectly polished high luster surface, free of porosity and scratches of any kind. The term originated in the marine and automotive industries. Examples of such a finish can be found on high quality boat hulls and automobiles. However, this quality of surface finish is achieved through two different procedures. Cars have primers and paint systems sprayed over medium quality metal surfaces. The paint flows into a self-leveling thin film and requires polishing to achieve a true Class A surface. The boat hull, however, receives its finish directly from the mold itself. If the mold has a Class A finish all the parts produced from it will also have the same high quality surface. Construction of quality molds can decrease final finishing time and increase overall part quality. Specular gloss (brightness, shine) can be measured easily using a gloss meter (BS 3900/ASTM D523-89) with reference to a standard surface, a viewing angle and a material color as described by Mathews et al. (3).

Several different techniques can be employed to achieve Class A surface finish such as:

- Finding the optimum chemical composition of the resin system. This will reduce shrinkage and ultimately, decrease the defects on the surface of the part. The types and quantities of resin, styrene, catalyst, inhibitor, accelerator, internal de-molding agent, external de-molding agent, charge, wetting agent, degassing agent and fiber reinforcement have to be optimized. In recent years, resins with low profile additives have been introduced to reduce shrinkage and enhance surface finish (4-6).
- Part and tool design. The quality and surface finish of a part depends highly on its design and on the surface finish of the mold. The mold should be designed in such a way to eliminate sharp edges and corners where it is difficult for the resin to reach. Gates and vents locations must be optimized in order to remove entrapped air and allow a smooth flow of the resin (7,8).
- Use of in-mold coating (IMC). In-mold coating and gel coat applications are being used to achieve optimum surface finish, which in most cases increase manufacturing time and cost (9).
- Selection of molding process parameters. For example, molding temperature, the upper and lower temperatures, injection rate or pressure, rate of cure and injection temperature as shown by Gauvin et al. (10), will also have an influence on part quality and surface finish.
- Secondary and finishing operations on the manufactured part (3,7). This is very often necessary in RTM and increases significantly the final manufacturing cost.

OBJECTIVES OF THE RESEARCH

The purpose of this research is to design a methodology based on some of the above-mentioned techniques in order to obtain a Class A surface finish. The chemical composition referred by Ford Motor Company Inc. is the starting point of this research. Their suggested chemical composition will be modified and optimized as the research progresses. The mold for making test components has been designed and manufactured by Ford Motor Company Inc., Detroit, MI. It was adapted for surface finish investigations in collaboration with Ecole Polytechnique and McGill University. A series of temperature and pressure sensors will be set up in the mold together with a data acquisition system. The emphasis will be on the modification of molding process parameters. Experiments will be designed using the Taguchi method of design of experiments (11,12). Taguchi control factors and their levels of influence will be identified. A matrix of experiments will be designed, experiments carried out and their results analyzed using statistical calculation software. Optimum levels and performance of the above mentioned control factors will be determined. In the end, verification experiments will be carried out. Ultimately, this investigation will provide a better understanding of surface finish aspects of the RTM process.

THE TAGUCHI METHOD

The Taguchi method refers to techniques of quality engineering that includes both statistical process control and innovative quality related management techniques. The Taguchi method leads to the best selection and setting of product/process design parameters and tolerances. The Taguchi method has become well known because it has led to major reductions in product/process development lead-time and has improved the manufacturability of complex products. The method analyzes, in a systematic way, the complex cause-effect relationship between design parameters and performance. This technique indicates how to design and perform experiments in order to investigate processes where the output depends on many factors (variables, inputs) without having to tediously and uneconomically run the process using all possible combinations of values of those variables. By systematically choosing certain combinations of variables, it is possible to separate their individual effects (11,12).

In order to determine and subsequently minimize the effect of factors that cause variation, the design cycle is divided into three phases: system design, parameter design, and tolerance design. In the first stage, the designer uses knowledge of the process being investigated to produce an initial design of a product or process. The objective of the second stage is to choose suitable values for the parameters of a product or process. In the third stage (tolerance design), higher quality parts replace less reliable components, improving the quality of the product or process (11,12). Parameter design is the focal point of this discussion. An overview of the Taguchi method (12) is shown in Figure 2.

Fig. 2 Flow chart of the Taguchi method

EXPERIMENTAL SETUP

The experimental setup contains a steel mold as shown in Figure 3. Its dimensions are 29.5" X 23.5". The mold consists of upper and lower plates in order to manufacture flat composite plates. Both plates have been refurbished to attain an excellent surface finish. The surface finish of the mold will be evaluated quantitatively. A picture frame is used between the two mold halves determining the thickness of the molded part. A set of different frames is available for various part thickness. The inside dimension of the picture frames is an 18"x18" square cavity. The frames are sealed to the plates using thin Teflon tape as gasket material.

The mold has a series of holes for the placement of pressure sensors, thermocouples, injection ports and vent gates. All the holes have the same dimensions allowing different configurations for sensors and gate placement. Therefore, the mold can either be filled by a central injection or a line injection using sensor ports at the circumference as injection ports. Injection can either be done from the bottom platen or from the top platen. The dimensions for the holes are specified by the pressure sensors. Therefore the thermocouples and injection plug are custom made to the same dimensions. The selected pressure sensor is a melt pressure transducer model PT422A made by Dynisco. These sensors are connected with a data acquisition system, which is System 6000 made by the Measurement Group Company.

Fig. 3 Steel plate mold for RTM process

This mold is mounted on a hydraulic press. The press has a capacity of 50 tons. Both platens are mounted on hydraulic pistons. The press can apply a pressure of about 2500 Psi. The press and mold are shown in Figure 4a.

Fig. 4 (a) Press with mounted mold (b) Heating system

(a)

(b)

Different heating systems were considered, including circulating oil, circulating water and heating cartridges. The final choice was a high efficiency, high flow rate water heating system. The maximum operating temperature is 120°C (see Figure 4b).

Scott Bader Crystic PD 9551 polyester resin will be optimized for minimum shrinkage and optimum surface finish. Other ingredients include accelerator (cobalt solution), catalyst (Tigonox 93) and filler (Omya BLR2).

SURFACE FINISH OPTIMIZATION PROCEDURE

The chemical reactions, manufacturing/molding parameters and tooling have been identified as the main parameters that affect the surface finish of the final part. The main objective of this research is to focus on the optimization of manufacturing parameters, which include molding temperature, upper and lower mold temperatures, injection rate, rate of cure and injection temperature. Three levels of performance for each of the above-mentioned factors would be considered for this research. An L_{18} Taguchi experimental array has been selected for carrying out experiments, which means that 18 experiments are necessary to find out the impact of each factor and each level. The factors and their corresponding levels are:

Table 1 Control factors and their levels

Factors	Level 1	Level 2	Level 3
Molding temperature (A)	70 C	85 C	100 C
Upper and lower mold temperature (B)	5 C	10 C	20 C
Injection rate (C) (depends on resin)	N-10%	Nominal (N)	N+10%
Rate of cure (D) (depends on DSC tests)	N-10%	Nominal (N)	N+10%
Injection temperature (E)	N-5 C	Nominal (N)	N+5 C

In other words, 18 flat plates will be manufactured using different quantitative levels of the above mentioned factors and the surface finish of each plate will be measured using a *QMS oblique angle optical diffusion device*, which gives surface finish on a percentage basis from 0 to 99.9. The Taguchi quality characteristics which will be used for interpretation of the results is *bigger is better* (12). Statistical numbers such as capability indices (C_p , C_{pk}), mean squared deviation, signal to noise ratio, standard deviation, variance and the percent contribution of each factor level will be calculated (11,12).

EXPERIMENTAL PLANNING

Many parameters are to be studied in order to master the RTM process. In this project, the surface finish of the final part is the key element to optimize. In order to do so, it is crucial to define a proper experimental plan to focus on the parameters that have the most influence on the end results.

Some mathematical models evaluate with statistical equations the different parameters involved in a process and permit the elaboration of an experimental plan to minimize the number of experiments and measurements. Using the Taguchi method 18 different experiments will be carried out with the factors and their corresponding levels listed in the following table:

Table 2 Experimental Matrix

Experiment #	Factor A	Factor B	Factor C	Factor D	Factor E
1	1	1	1	1	1
2	1	2	2	2	2
3	1	3	3	3	3
4	2	1	1	2	2
5	2	2	2	3	3
6	2	3	3	1	1
7	3	1	2	1	3
8	3	2	3	2	1
9	3	3	1	3	2
10	1	1	3	3	2
11	1	2	1	1	3
12	1	3	2	2	1
13	2	1	2	3	1
14	2	2	3	1	2
15	2	3	1	2	3
16	3	1	3	2	3
17	3	2	1	3	1
18	3	3	2	1	2

TEST RESULTS

The experimental matrix shown in table 2 is being executed. Preliminary tests have shown common manufacturing problems such as dry spots air bubbles and fabric print through on the surface. A comprehensive analysis of surface issues will be presented based on all results.

CONCLUSION

An experimental procedure based on the Taguchi method has been proposed to study the process parameters that influence surface finish in RTM process. The plan of experiments, which has been described in this paper, is in progress. The authors are working on the results and their interpretation. More experiments will be designed and carried out for the validation of results.

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